

The Gender Gap in the Field of Architecture

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Abstract:- Gender and the profession of architecture in Nigeria were the subjects of this study. The gender gap in the architectural profession, particularly in terms of membership, certification, experience, project types, and work schedule, was briefly examined. Using a structured questionnaire, a sample of certified architects from the North Central, South East, and South Western regions of the countries was selected. The findings demonstrated that approximately a quarter of Nigeria's architects were female. It also demonstrated that architects' professional experience is significantly influenced by gender differentiation. On the other hand, gender has little effect on the kinds of projects that architects participate in or the professional services they provide. Despite the fact that female architects can perform many of the same tasks as men, the architectural profession in Nigeria is still heavily dominated by men. As a result, Nigeria's training, employment, and retention of architects must be more gender-inclusive.

I. INTRODUCTION

Although most of the time used as a shorthand for women, gender refers to the socially and culturally constructed roles for men and women (Makama, 2013) or masculinity and femininity (Oakley, 1985). According to Hayes (2017), it is regarded as the organization and social construction of sexual difference. Society divides humanity into genders based on biological differences, and sex is the basis for this division. (Ademuson, NY) It is also the idea of a man and a woman who exist in a particular location at a particular time, as well as the results of the roles they are given. As a result, the terms "gender gap," "gender inequality," "gendering," and other similar expressions all refer to the marginalization of one gender in favor of the other. Because professions in the fields of medicine, law,

and engineering, as well as those in the construction industry, were initially dominated by men, gendering professions and professionals was a quiet task. It is a situation in which men and women rarely receive equal treatment in career development, training, certification, recruitment, emolument, and other career-related areas. This constitutes gender-based professional career discrimination.

According to Davis (1996), the issue of women's discontent—whether in a small or large number—continues to be the subject of discussion in a variety of professional spheres. Even though more women appear to be graduating from law school, there is still a significant gender gap in the legal profession (Chan, 2017). After they finished their training, gender was thought to play a significant role (Reece, 2000). According to Hagan, Zatz, Arnold, & Kay (1991), the legal profession is predominantly male. It was observed that the legal community has historically restricted gender diversity, disadvantaging women and minority groups.

Additionally, issues of accounting professional equality have been discussed in the profession (Kyriacou, 2000). According to Kirkland and Loft (1993), some studies have shown that the profession has a male-dominated hierarchy. (2008) Haynes Diversity initiatives like inclusive hiring, promotion, and organizational environment (Bacchi & Eveline, 2009) were necessary due to the profession's male dominance. Since professional engineering is perceived as masculine, this issue does not leave the engineering field behind (Phipps, 2002). According to Evetts (1994), the engineering profession has a reputation for being tough, heavy, filthy, and masculine. A sense of physical masculinity pervades the profession to the detriment of women, and women are frequently relegated to non-technical support roles (Carter and Kirkop, 1990).

One of the most gender-blind sectors is the construction industry. Sang and Pavel (2012) pointed out that gender inequality persists in the construction industry, which is still dominated by men. According to Whittock (2010), women have not sufficiently challenged the established notion of what it means to be a "women" in the construction industry's non-traditional employment. According to Agapiolu (2002), who wrote about the Scottish construction industry, women are more likely to hold clerical and secretarial positions than skilled and semi-skilled ones. The construction industry's gender skewedness is quite alarming when compared to other industries (Sommerville, Kennedy, & Orr, 1993), and the low number of women working in skilled professions is well documented (Bagihole, Dainty, & Neale, 2000). In fact, according to Sang and Powel (2012), legislation promoting equality in employment is not achieving much in the construction industry due to the industry's largely male workforce. These authors cited sources that talked about the challenges faced by women in the construction industry. According to Sang and Powel, who cited ONS (2009), the number of women working in the construction industry in the United Kingdom is only 10%, compared to the number of women working in other industries (Shanmugam, Amaratunga, Haigh, Elvitigala, Baldry, & Ruddock). 2007). According to Clarke (2016), despite the fact that there is a rise in the number of women enrolling in construction-related schools, only a small percentage end up working in the industry.

As a subset of the construction industry, the architectural profession did not fare any better. According to Caven (2006), architecture was regarded as a profession for men. It has been discovered that there are few women architects in the majority of advanced nations. Women architects make up 14% of registered architects in the UK, for instance (RIBA, 2002). The circumstance is comparable in nations like Canada and Australia (RAIA 1991) (Philips, 2017). According to de Graft-Johnson, Manley, & Greed (2005), it was discovered that despite an increase in female enrollment in architecture schools, the expected increase in the number of qualified female architects was not realized. 2005, Whitman) Architecture is heavily male-dominated in the United States. According to Stratigakos (2016), despite the fact that women make up nearly half of architecture school graduates, fewer than 20% are licensed to practice. It was demonstrated that, across all age groups, the profession

of architecture has the lowest proportion of women in Australia compared to the professions of law, medicine, and accounting.

The profession of architect in Nigeria dates back to the colonial era, when expatriates from the United Kingdom dominated the construction and building industry. The first indigenous architecture school began instructing future Nigerian architects at the beginning of the 1950s. The graduates were exempt from part II of the Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA) professional examination with diploma certificates. The school of architecture began awarding Bachelor's and Masters' degrees in architecture (B.Sc. and M.Sc. Architecture) after Nigeria gained independence in 1960. More architecture schools opened in the country in the 1970s. Under the supervision of the Architects Registration Council of Nigeria (ARCON), there are currently more than 25 architecture degree-granting schools in Nigeria. Since it was established by decree in 1962, ARCON has continued to provide internship training, examine and moderate the certification of Nigerian architects. They collaborate with the Nigerian Institute of Architects (NIA), a group of professional architects established in 1960, on these tasks. As a result, Nigeria's architecture industry can be said to have developed over time. Before Nigeria's independence in 1960, expatriates worked for the colonial government there. Later, Nigerian architects trained in the UK and US joined in. After independence, indigenously trained architects have maintained the profession's growth to this day.

II. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to gain an understanding of the gender gap in the profession of architecture in Nigeria. The study examined architectural firms in Lagos, Enugu, and Abuja, three cities in the west, east, and central parts of Nigeria, using a questionnaire survey design. The Nigerian cities with the highest concentrations of architectural firms are Lagos and Abuja. According to ARCON (2013), there were 190 firms in Abuja, 57 in Enugu, and 289 in Lagos. For the purpose of administering the questionnaire, two architects were purposefully selected from one of every two architectural firms. Out of the 536 questionnaires that were distributed, 408 were retrieved or 76%.

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 Gender Distribution in Questionnaire

Gender	Freq.	%
Male	309	75.7
Female	99	24.3
Total	408	100.0

Table 2 Representation based on Gender in ARCON

Registered with ARCON	Male %	Freq.	Female%	Freq.
Yes	309	100.0	99	100.0
No	0	0	0	0.0
Total	309	100.0	99	100.0

Table 3 Number of ARCON Registered Architectural Firms in Nigeria based on Selected States

Firm Location	Male	Freq. %	Female	Freq. %
Abuja	118	38.19	25	25.25
Enugu	26	8.41	5	5.05
Lagos	165	53.40	69	69.70
Total	309	100.0	99	100.0

Table 4 Academic Qualification of Architects based on Gender

Education	Male	Freq. %	Female	Freq. %
HND	7	2.27	2	2.02
B.Sc	9	2.91	1	1.01
PGD	6	1.94	1	1.01
M.Sc	271	87.70	82	82.83
M.Phil/Ph.D	16	5.18	13	13.13
Total	309	100.0	99	100

The discoveries showed that of the relative multitude of 408 engineers inspected, around 75.7% were guys and generally 25% were females. This goes quite far to authenticate different examinations about orientation and calling. For this situation, ladies address a fourth of the complete number of planners. Regarding proficient certificate, every one of the draftsmen inspected (408) have been ensured by the Engineers Enrollment Board of Nigeria (ARCON) which shows that the female designers are not sub-par compared to their male partners. These female

modelers likewise brag of good scholarly capabilities with over 80% of them having a post advanced education in engineering. Nigerian female engineers are seen here to contrast well and their male partners. It became obvious accordingly that separated from the offer mathematical benefit male engineers have over their female associates; any remaining demographical qualities considered in this study showed that the two are at standard particularly in scholastic preparation and expert affirmation.

Table 5 Classification of Professional Qualification based of Age between Genders

Gender and Professional Experience of Architects in Building Industry Years Post Professional Qualifications was obtained	Male n (%)	Female n (%)
36 – 45 years	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
26 – 35 years	8 (100.0)	0 (0.0)
16 – 25 years	35 (85.4)	6 (14.6)
6 – 15 years	87 (68.0)	41 (32.0)
Less than 6 years	179 (77.5)	52 (22.5)
Total	309 (75.7)	99 (24.3)

$$\chi^2 = 9.2204 \text{ df} = 3 \text{ p} = 0.026$$

According to Table 5, there is a significant correlation between the professional experience of architects and their gender when gender is taken into consideration. The Chi-square test, which was used to determine whether architects' gender has a significant impact on their professional experience, revealed that architects' gender had a significant impact on their professional experience. The duration of their professional experience is defined as the number of years between the time they passed their final professional exam and the time this study was conducted. The conclusion demonstrates that no architect had more than 45 years of post-professional experience.

In the sample of architects, there were no female architects with post-professional experience of between 26 and 35 years. In addition, it revealed that 14.6% of 41 architects with 16-25 years of post-professional experience were female and 85.4% were male. Furthermore, 68.0% of the 128 architects with six to fifteen years of post-professional experience were male and 32.0% were female. Finally, the findings demonstrated a significant relationship (p = 0.026) between architects' gender and their post-

professional experience in Nigeria. This suggests that it is challenging to long-term retain female architects in an industry dominated by men with more professional experience. According to some studies (IES, 1995), women leave the industry due to a lack of job opportunities and opportunities for advancement. This may necessitate increased efforts to retain and advance more female architects.

IV. CONCLUSION

According to the findings of the study, the profession of architecture in Nigeria is largely dominated by men. However, this does not imply that women are putting in less effort than men, as female architects are just as qualified as men in every way. The majority of female architects receive adequate education, even up to postgraduate level. This means that female planners are not blocked by the difficulties presented by scholarly prerequisites. Despite the rigorous process of professional certification, Nigerian female architects are not discouraged from pursuing a career in architecture. Therefore, it is impossible to attribute the

gender gap in Nigeria's architecture industry solely to academic or professional factors; other factors are likely to be at play. However, efforts must be made to encourage more women to pursue careers in architecture and other male-dominated fields, particularly in Nigeria's construction sector.

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